

4-total edge product cordial for some star related graphs

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ABSTRACT

Let $G = (V(G), E(G))$ be a graph, define an edge labeling function ψ from $E(G)$ to $\{0, 1, \dots, k-1\}$ where k is an integer, $2 \leq k \leq |E(G)|$, induces a vertex labeling function ψ^* from $V(G)$ to $\{0, 1, \dots, k-1\}$ such that $\psi^*(v) = \psi(e_1) \times \psi(e_2) \times \dots \times \psi(e_n) \pmod k$ where e_1, e_2, \dots, e_n are all edge incident to v . This function ψ is called a k -total edge product cordial (or simply k -TEPC) labeling of G if the absolute difference between number of vertices and edges labeling with i and number of vertices and edges labeling with j no more than 1 for all $i, j \in \{0, 1, \dots, k-1\}$. In this paper, 4-total edge product cordial labeling for some star related graphs are determined.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Let us begin with a graph $G = (V(G), E(G))$ that is simple, connected, finite and undirected with order p and size q . With regards to the standard terminology and notation, we refer to books [1]-[4]. We also provide a brief summary of definitions that are invaluable for the present study.

A graph labeling is an assignment of integers to edges or vertices or both subject to certain conditions. If the domain of the mapping is the set of edges (or vertices) then the labeling is called an edge labeling (or a vertex labeling). For a labeling function ψ , an edge e (or a vertex v) is an i -edge (or an i -vertex) if $\psi(e) = i$ (or $\psi(v) = i$) where $i \in Z$. Denote the number of i -edges (or i -vertices) of G under ψ by $e_\psi(i)$ (or $v_\psi(i)$), respectively and let $\psi(i) = e_\psi(i) + v_\psi(i)$.

Labeling graph has applications in coding theory, especially for the design of good radar type codes, missile guidance codes, and convolution codes with optimal autocorrelation properties. Labeling graph plays important role in the study of communication network and X-ray crystallography. A detailed study of some applications of labeling graphs are given in [5]-[9].

A lot of researchers have written on cordial labeling. Cahit [10] introduced cordial labeling and there are many papers studied cordial graph of some graphs such as [11], [12]. Sundaram *et al.* [13] defined product cordial labeling and in [14]-[16] some researchers illustrate product cordial labeling of some graphs. Vadiya and Barasara [17], [18] proposed two definitions edge product cordial labeling and total edge product cordial labeling.

Azaizeh *et al.* [19] introduced k -total edge product cordial labeling which is:

Definition 1. let ψ be an edge labeling function from $E(G)$ to $\{0, 1, \dots, k-1\}$ where k is an integer, $2 \leq k \leq |E(G)|$. For each vertex v , assign the label $\psi(e_1) \times \psi(e_2) \times \dots \times \psi(e_n) \pmod k$ where e_1, e_2, \dots, e_n are the

edges incident to vertex v . The function ψ is called a k -total edge product cordial (or simply k -TEPC) labeling of G if $|(v_\psi(i) + e_\psi(i)) - (v_\psi(j) + e_\psi(j))| \leq 1$, for $i, j \in \{0, 1, \dots, k-1\}$. A graph G with a k -total edge product cordial labeling is called k -total edge product cordial graph.

Some researchers studied graphs in k -total edge product cordial labeling [19]-[23]. Vadiya *et al.* [24] studied cordial labeling for some star related graphs and Hasni and Azaizah [25] determined 3-total edge products cordial labeling for some star related graphs. As a continuation of these results and the results in [19], [21], the main aim of this paper is to determine the 4-total edge product cordial labeling for some star related graphs.

2. MAIN RESULT

Let $K_{1,n}$ denote the star with order $n+1$. We first give brief summary of definitions which are useful for our investigations.

Definition 2. [24] consider two stars $K_{1,n}^{(1)}$ and $K_{1,n}^{(2)}$, then $G = \langle K_{1,n}^{(1)}, K_{1,n}^{(2)} \rangle$ is the graph obtained by joining apex vertices of stars to a new vertex x . Note that G has $2n+3$ vertices and $2n+2$ edges.

Definition 3. [24] consider k copies of stars namely $K_{1,n}^{(1)}, K_{1,n}^{(2)}, \dots, K_{1,n}^{(k)}$. Then $G = \langle K_{1,n}^{(1)}, K_{1,n}^{(2)}, \dots, K_{1,n}^{(k)} \rangle$ is the graph obtained by joining apex vertices of each $K_{1,n}^{(p-1)}$ and $K_{1,n}^{(p)}$ to a new vertex x_{p-1} where $2 \leq p \leq k$. Note that G has $k(n+2)-1$ vertices and $k(n+2)-2$ edges.

Theorem 1 Graph $\langle K_{1,n}^{(1)}, K_{1,n}^{(2)}, \dots, K_{1,n}^{(k)} \rangle$ is 4-TEPC for all $n \geq 3, k \geq 1$, except when $n \equiv 1$ or $2 \pmod{4}$, $k=1$ or $n=3, k=1$.

Proof. Let $V(\langle K_{1,n}^{(1)}, K_{1,n}^{(2)}, \dots, K_{1,n}^{(k)} \rangle) = \{u^{(j)}, v_i^{(j)}, 1 \leq j \leq k, 1 \leq i \leq n\} \cup \{x_m, 1 \leq m \leq k-1\}$ and $E(\langle K_{1,n}^{(1)}, K_{1,n}^{(2)}, \dots, K_{1,n}^{(k)} \rangle) = \{u^{(j)}v_i^{(j)}, 1 \leq j \leq k, 1 \leq i \leq n\} \cup \{u^{(j)}x_j, u^{(j+1)}x_j, 1 \leq j \leq k-1\}$. We consider the following cases.

Case 1: $k \equiv 0 \pmod{4}$.

Case 1.1: $n \equiv 0 \pmod{4}$.

Define ψ be an edge labeling function from $E(G)$ to $\{0, 1, 2, 3\}$:

$$\begin{aligned} \psi(u^{(1)}v_1^{(1)}) &= 1 \\ \psi(u^{(1)}v_i^{(1)}) &= 0, 2 \leq i \leq \frac{n}{4} \\ \psi(u^{(j)}v_i^{(j)}) &= 0, 2 \leq j \leq k, 1 \leq i \leq \frac{n}{4} \\ \psi(u^{(j)}v_i^{(j)}) &= 1, 1 \leq j \leq k, \frac{n+4}{4} \leq i \leq \frac{n}{2} \\ \psi(u^{(j)}v_i^{(j)}) &= 2, 1 \leq j \leq k, \frac{n+2}{2} \leq i \leq \frac{3n}{4} \\ \psi(u^{(j)}v_i^{(j)}) &= 3, 1 \leq j \leq k, \frac{3n+4}{4} \leq i \leq n \\ \psi(u^{(4j-3)}x_{4j-3}) &= 2, 1 \leq j \leq \frac{k}{4} \\ \psi(u^{(4j-2)}x_{4j-3}) &= 3, 1 \leq j \leq \frac{k}{4} \\ \psi(u^{(4j-2)}x_{4j-2}) &= 3, 1 \leq j \leq \frac{k}{4} \\ \psi(u^{(4j-1)}x_{4j-2}) &= 1, 1 \leq j \leq \frac{k}{4} \\ \psi(u^{(4j-1)}x_{4j-1}) &= 2, 1 \leq j \leq \frac{k}{4} \\ \psi(u^{(4)}x_3) &= 2 \\ \psi(u^{(4j)}x_{4j}) &= 1, 1 \leq j \leq \frac{k-4}{4} \\ \psi(u^{(4j+1)}x_{4j}) &= 1, 1 \leq j \leq \frac{k-4}{4} \end{aligned}$$

Case 1.2: $n \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$.

Define ψ be an edge labeling function from $E(G)$ to $\{0, 1, 2, 3\}$:

$$\begin{aligned} \psi(u^{(j)}v_i^{(j)}) &= 0, 1 \leq j \leq k, 1 \leq i \leq \frac{n-1}{4} \\ \psi(u^{(j)}v_i^{(j)}) &= 2, 1 \leq j \leq k, \frac{n+3}{4} \leq i \leq \frac{n-1}{2} \\ \psi(u^{(2j-1)}v_i^{(2j-1)}) &= 1, 1 \leq j \leq \frac{k}{2}, \frac{n+1}{2} \leq i \leq \frac{3n-3}{4} \\ \psi(u^{(2j-1)}v_i^{(2j-1)}) &= 3, 1 \leq j \leq \frac{k}{2}, \frac{3n+1}{4} \leq i \leq n \\ \psi(u^{(2j)}v_i^{(2j)}) &= 3, 1 \leq j \leq \frac{k}{2}, \frac{n+1}{2} \leq i \leq \frac{3n-3}{4} \\ \psi(u^{(2j)}v_i^{(2j)}) &= 1, 1 \leq j \leq \frac{k}{2}, \frac{3n+1}{4} \leq i \leq n \\ \psi(u^{(4j-3)}x_{4j-3}) &= 2, 1 \leq j \leq \frac{k}{4} \\ \psi(u^{(4j-2)}x_{4j-3}) &= 3, 1 \leq j \leq \frac{k}{4} \\ \psi(u^{(4j-2)}x_{4j-2}) &= 2, 1 \leq j \leq \frac{k}{4} \\ \psi(u^{(4j-1)}x_{4j-2}) &= 1, 1 \leq j \leq \frac{k}{4} \\ \psi(u^{(4j-1)}x_{4j-1}) &= 2, 1 \leq j \leq \frac{k}{4} \\ \psi(u^{(4)}x_3) &= 2 \\ \psi(u^{(4j)}x_{4j-1}) &= 1, 2 \leq j \leq \frac{k}{4} \\ \psi(u^{(4j)}x_{4j}) &= 0, 1 \leq j \leq \frac{k-4}{4} \\ \psi(u^{(4j+1)}x_{4j}) &= 3, 1 \leq j \leq \frac{k-4}{4} \end{aligned}$$

Case 1.3: $n \equiv 2 \pmod{4}$.

Define ψ be an edge labeling function from $E(G)$ to $\{0, 1, 2, 3\}$:

$$\begin{aligned} \psi(u^{(j)}v_i^{(j)}) &= 0, 1 \leq j \leq k, 1 \leq i \leq \frac{n-2}{4} \\ \psi(u^{(2j-1)}v_i^{(2j-1)}) &= 1, 1 \leq j \leq \frac{k}{2}, \frac{n+2}{4} \leq i \leq \frac{n}{2} \\ \psi(u^{(2j-1)}v_i^{(2j-1)}) &= 3, 1 \leq j \leq \frac{k}{2}, \frac{n+2}{2} \leq i \leq \frac{3n+2}{4} \\ \psi(u^{(2j-1)}v_i^{(2j-1)}) &= 2, 1 \leq j \leq \frac{k}{2}, \frac{3n+6}{4} \leq i \leq n \\ \psi(u^{(4j-2)}v_i^{(4j-2)}) &= 1, 1 \leq j \leq \frac{k}{4}, \frac{n+2}{4} \leq i \leq \frac{n}{2} \\ \psi(u^{(4j-2)}v_i^{(4j-2)}) &= 2, 1 \leq j \leq \frac{k}{4}, \frac{n+2}{2} \leq i \leq \frac{3n+2}{4} \\ \psi(u^{(4j)}v_i^{(4j)}) &= 2, 1 \leq j \leq \frac{k}{4}, \frac{n+2}{4} \leq i \leq \frac{n}{2} \\ \psi(u^{(4j)}v_i^{(4j)}) &= 3, 1 \leq j \leq \frac{k}{4}, \frac{n+2}{2} \leq i \leq \frac{3n+2}{4} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \psi(u^{(4j)}v_i^{(4j)}) &= 1, 1 \leq j \leq \frac{k}{4}, \frac{3n+6}{4} \leq i \leq n \\ \psi(u^{(4j-3)}x_{4j-3}) &= 2, 1 \leq j \leq \frac{k}{4} \\ \psi(u^{(4j-2)}x_{4j-3}) &= 2, 1 \leq j \leq \frac{k}{4} \\ \psi(u^{(4j-2)}x_{4j-2}) &= 0, 1 \leq j \leq \frac{k}{4} \\ \psi(u^{(4j-1)}x_{4j-2}) &= 1, 1 \leq j \leq \frac{k}{4} \\ \psi(u^{(4j-1)}x_{4j-1}) &= 3, 1 \leq j \leq \frac{k}{4} \\ \psi(u^{(4)}x_3) &= 2 \\ \psi(u^{(4j)}x_{4j-1}) &= 1, 2 \leq j \leq \frac{k}{4} \\ \psi(u^{(4j)}x_{4j}) &= 2, 1 \leq j \leq \frac{k-4}{4} \\ \psi(u^{(4j+1)}x_{4j}) &= 2, 1 \leq j \leq \frac{k-4}{4} \end{aligned}$$

Case 1.4: $n \equiv 3 \pmod{4}$.

Define ψ be an edge labeling function from $E(G)$ to $\{0, 1, 2, 3\}$:

$$\begin{aligned} \psi(u^{(j)}v_i^{(j)}) &= 0, 1 \leq j \leq k, 1 \leq i \leq \frac{n-3}{4} \\ \psi(u^{(j)}v_i^{(j)}) &= 1, 1 \leq j \leq k, \frac{n+1}{4} \leq i \leq \frac{n-1}{2} \\ \psi(u^{(j)}v_i^{(j)}) &= 2, 1 \leq j \leq k, \frac{n+1}{2} \leq i \leq \frac{3n-1}{4} \\ \psi(u^{(j)}v_i^{(j)}) &= 3, 1 \leq j \leq k, \frac{3n+3}{4} \leq i \leq n \\ \psi(u^{(2j-1)}x_{2j-1}) &= 0, 1 \leq j \leq \frac{k}{2} \\ \psi(u^{(2)}x_1) &= 3 \\ \psi(u^{(2j)}x_{2j-1}) &= 0, 2 \leq j \leq \frac{k}{2} \\ \psi(u^{(4j-2)}x_{4j-2}) &= 2, 1 \leq j \leq \frac{k}{4} \\ \psi(u^{(4j)}x_{4j}) &= 3, 1 \leq j \leq \frac{k-4}{4} \\ \psi(u^{(2j+1)}x_{2j}) &= 1, 1 \leq j \leq \frac{k-2}{2}. \end{aligned}$$

We now have $\psi(0) = \psi(1) = \psi(3) = \frac{k}{2}(n+2) - 1$, $\psi(2) = \frac{k}{2}(n+2)$. Therefore, $|\psi(i) - \psi(j)| \leq 1$ for $0 \leq i < j \leq 3$. Hence ψ is 4-TEPC labeling.

Case 2: $k \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$.

Case 2.1: $n \equiv 0 \pmod{4}$.

Define ψ be an edge labeling function from $E(G)$ to $\{0, 1, 2, 3\}$:

$$\psi(u^{(j)}v_i^{(j)}) = 0, 1 \leq j \leq k, 1 \leq i \leq \frac{n}{4}$$

$$\begin{aligned}\psi(u^{(j)}v_i^{(j)}) &= 1, 1 \leq j \leq k, \frac{n+4}{4} \leq i \leq \frac{n}{2} \\ \psi(u^{(j)}v_i^{(j)}) &= 2, 1 \leq j \leq k, \frac{n+2}{2} \leq i \leq \frac{3n}{4} \\ \psi(u^{(j)}v_i^{(j)}) &= 3, 1 \leq j \leq k, \frac{3n+4}{4} \leq i \leq n \\ \psi(u^{(2j-1)}x_{2j-1}) &= 2, 1 \leq j \leq \frac{k-1}{2} \\ \psi(u^{(2j)}x_{2j}) &= 3, 1 \leq j \leq \frac{k-1}{2} \\ \psi(u^{(j+1)}x_j) &= 1, 1 \leq j \leq k-1.\end{aligned}$$

We now have $\psi(0) = \frac{k}{2}(n+2)$, $\psi(1) = \psi(2) = \psi(3) = \frac{k}{2}(n+2) - 1$. Therefore, $|\psi(i) - \psi(j)| \leq 1$ for $0 \leq i < j \leq 3$. Hence ψ is 4-TEPC labeling.

Case 2.2: $n \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$, $k \neq 1$.

Define ψ be an edge labeling function from $E(G)$ to $\{0, 1, 2, 3\}$:

$$\begin{aligned}\psi(u^{(j)}v_i^{(j)}) &= 0, 1 \leq j \leq k, 1 \leq i \leq \frac{n-1}{4} \\ \psi(u^{(j)}v_i^{(j)}) &= 1, 1 \leq j \leq k, \frac{n+3}{4} \leq i \leq \frac{n-1}{2} \\ \psi(u^{(2j-1)}v_i^{(2j-1)}) &= 3, 1 \leq j \leq \frac{k+1}{2}, \frac{n+1}{2} \leq i \leq \frac{3n-3}{4} \\ \psi(u^{(2j-1)}v_i^{(2j-1)}) &= 2, 1 \leq j \leq \frac{k+1}{2}, \frac{3n+1}{4} \leq i \leq n \\ \psi(u^{(2j)}v_i^{(2j)}) &= 2, 1 \leq j \leq \frac{k-1}{2}, \frac{n+1}{2} \leq i \leq \frac{3n-3}{4} \\ \psi(u^{(2j)}v_i^{(2j)}) &= 3, 1 \leq j \leq \frac{k-1}{2}, \frac{3n+1}{4} \leq i \leq n \\ \psi(u^{(4j-3)}x_{4j-3}) &= 0, 1 \leq j \leq \frac{k-1}{4} \\ \psi(u^{(4j-2)}x_{4j-3}) &= 3, 1 \leq j \leq \frac{k-1}{4} \\ \psi(u^{(4j-1)}x_{4j-1}) &= 3, 1 \leq j \leq \frac{k-1}{4} \\ \psi(u^{(4)}x_3) &= 3 \\ \psi(u^{(4j)}x_{4j-1}) &= 2, 2 \leq j \leq \frac{k-1}{4} \\ \psi(u^{(2j)}x_{2j}) &= 1, 1 \leq j \leq \frac{k-1}{2} \\ \psi(u^{(2j+1)}x_{2j}) &= 1, 1 \leq j \leq \frac{k-1}{2}.\end{aligned}$$

We now have $\psi(0) = \psi(1) = \psi(3) = \frac{k(n+2)-1}{2}$, $\psi(2) = \frac{k(n+2)-3}{2}$. Therefore, $|\psi(i) - \psi(j)| \leq 1$ for $0 \leq i < j \leq 3$. Hence ψ is 4-TEPC labeling.

Case 2.3: $n \equiv 2 \pmod{4}$, $k \neq 1$.

Define ψ be an edge labeling function from $E(G)$ to $\{0, 1, 2, 3\}$:

$$\begin{aligned}\psi(u^{(j)}v_i^{(j)}) &= 0, 1 \leq j \leq k, 1 \leq i \leq \frac{n-2}{4} \\ \psi(u^{(2j-1)}v_i^{(2j-1)}) &= 1, 1 \leq j \leq \frac{k+1}{2}, \frac{n+2}{2} \leq i \leq \frac{3n+2}{4}\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \psi(u^{(2j-1)}v_i^{(2j-1)}) &= 3, 1 \leq j \leq \frac{k+1}{2}, \frac{3n+6}{4} \leq i \leq n \\ \psi(u^{(2j)}v_i^{(2j)}) &= 3, 1 \leq j \leq \frac{k-1}{2}, \frac{n+2}{2} \leq i \leq \frac{3n+2}{4} \\ \psi(u^{(2j)}v_i^{(2j)}) &= 1, 1 \leq j \leq \frac{k-1}{2}, \frac{3n+6}{4} \leq i \leq n \\ \psi(u^{(2j-1)}x_{2j-1}) &= 0, 1 \leq j \leq \frac{k-1}{2} \\ \psi(u^{(2j)}x_{2j}) &= 3, 1 \leq j \leq \frac{k-1}{2} \\ \psi(u^{(2)}x_1) &= 3 \\ \psi(u^{(j)}x_{j-1}) &= 1, 3 \leq j \leq k. \end{aligned}$$

We now have $\psi(0) = \psi(1) = \psi(3) = \frac{k}{2}(n+2) - 1$, $\psi(2) = \frac{k}{2}(n+2)$. Therefore, $|\psi(i) - \psi(j)| \leq 1$ for $0 \leq i < j \leq 3$. Hence ψ is 4-TEPC labeling.

Case 2.4: $n \equiv 3 \pmod{4}$.

Define ψ be an edge labeling function from $E(G)$ to $\{0, 1, 2, 3\}$:

$$\begin{aligned} \psi(u^{(j)}v_i^{(j)}) &= 0, 1 \leq j \leq k, 1 \leq i \leq \frac{n-3}{4} \\ \psi(u^{(j)}v_i^{(j)}) &= 1, 1 \leq j \leq k, \frac{n+1}{4} \leq i \leq \frac{n-1}{2} \\ \psi(u^{(j)}v_i^{(j)}) &= 2, 1 \leq j \leq k, \frac{n+1}{2} \leq i \leq \frac{3n-1}{4} \\ \psi(u^{(j)}v_i^{(j)}) &= 3, 1 \leq j \leq k, \frac{3n+3}{4} \leq i \leq n \\ \psi(u^{(2j)}x_{2j}) &= 0, 1 \leq j \leq \frac{k-1}{2} \\ \psi(u^{(2j+1)}x_{2j}) &= 0, 1 \leq j \leq \frac{k-1}{2} \\ \psi(u^{(4j-3)}x_{4j-3}) &= 2, 1 \leq j \leq \frac{k-1}{4} \\ \psi(u^{(4j-1)}x_{4j-1}) &= 3, 1 \leq j \leq \frac{k-1}{4} \\ \psi(u^{(2j)}x_{2j-1}) &= 1, 1 \leq j \leq \frac{k-1}{2} \end{aligned}$$

We now have $\psi(0) = \frac{k(n+2)-3}{2}$, $\psi(1) = \psi(2) = \psi(3) = \frac{k(n+2)-1}{2}$. Therefore, $|\psi(i) - \psi(j)| \leq 1$ for $0 \leq i < j \leq 3$. Hence ψ is 4-TEPC labeling.

Case 3: $k \equiv 2 \pmod{4}$.

Case 3.1: $n \equiv 0 \pmod{4}$.

Define ψ be an edge labeling function from $E(G)$ to $\{0, 1, 2, 3\}$:

$$\begin{aligned} \psi(u^{(1)}v_1^{(1)}) &= 2 \\ \psi(u^{(1)}v_i^{(1)}) &= 1, 2 \leq i \leq \frac{n}{2} \\ \psi(u^{(1)}v_i^{(1)}) &= 3, \frac{n+2}{2} \leq i \leq n \\ \psi(u^{(2)}v_1^{(2)}) &= 1 \\ \psi(u^{(2)}v_2^{(2)}) &= 3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \psi(u^{(2)}v_i^{(2)}) &= 0, 3 \leq i \leq \frac{n+2}{2} \\ \psi(u^{(2)}v_i^{(2)}) &= 2, \frac{n+4}{2} \leq i \leq n \\ \psi(u^{(j)}v_i^{(j)}) &= 0, 3 \leq j \leq k, 1 \leq i \leq \frac{n}{4} \\ \psi(u^{(j)}v_i^{(j)}) &= 1, 3 \leq j \leq k, \frac{n+4}{4} \leq i \leq \frac{n}{2} \\ \psi(u^{(j)}v_i^{(j)}) &= 2, 3 \leq j \leq k, \frac{n+2}{2} \leq i \leq \frac{3n}{4} \\ \psi(u^{(j)}v_i^{(j)}) &= 3, 3 \leq j \leq k, \frac{3n+4}{4} \\ \psi(u^{(j)}x_j) &= 1, 1 \leq j \leq k-1 \\ \psi(u^{(2)}x_1) &= 0 \\ \psi(u^{(2j)}x_{2j-1}) &= 2, 2 \leq j \leq \frac{k}{2} \\ \psi(u^{(2j+1)}x_{2j}) &= 3, 1 \leq j \leq \frac{k-2}{2}. \end{aligned}$$

We now have $\psi(0) = \psi(1) = \psi(2) = \frac{k}{2}(n+2) - 1$, $\psi(3) = \frac{k}{2}(n+2)$. Therefore, $|\psi(i) - \psi(j)| \leq 1$ for $0 \leq i < j \leq 3$. Hence ψ is 4-TEPC labeling.

Case 3.2: $n \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$.

Define ψ be an edge labeling function from $E(G)$ to $\{0, 1, 2, 3\}$:

$$\begin{aligned} \psi(u^{(j)}v_i^{(j)}) &= 0, 1 \leq j \leq k, 1 \leq i \leq \frac{n-1}{4} \\ \psi(u^{(j)}v_i^{(j)}) &= 1, 1 \leq j \leq k, \frac{n+3}{4} \leq i \leq \frac{n-1}{2} \\ \psi(u^{(2j-1)}v_i^{(2j-1)}) &= 2, 1 \leq j \leq \frac{k}{2}, \frac{n+1}{2} \leq i \leq \frac{3n-3}{4} \\ \psi(u^{(2j-1)}v_i^{(2j-1)}) &= 3, 1 \leq j \leq \frac{k}{2}, \frac{3n+1}{4} \leq i \leq n \\ \psi(u^{(2j)}v_i^{(2j)}) &= 3, 1 \leq j \leq \frac{k}{2}, \frac{n+1}{2} \leq i \leq \frac{3n-3}{4} \\ \psi(u^{(2j)}v_i^{(2j)}) &= 2, 1 \leq j \leq \frac{k}{2}, \frac{3n+1}{4} \leq i \leq n \\ \psi(u^{(j)}x_j) &= 1, 1 \leq j \leq k-1 \\ \psi(u^{(4j-2)}x_{4j-3}) &= 1, 1 \leq j \leq \frac{k+2}{4} \\ \psi(u^{(4j-1)}x_{4j-2}) &= 0, 1 \leq j \leq \frac{k-2}{4} \\ \psi(u^{(4j)}x_{4j-1}) &= 2, 1 \leq j \leq \frac{k-2}{4} \\ \psi(u^{(4j+1)}x_{4j}) &= 3, 1 \leq j \leq \frac{k-2}{4}. \end{aligned}$$

We now have $\psi(0) = \psi(2) = \psi(3) = \frac{k}{2}(n+2) - 1$, $\psi(1) = \frac{k}{2}(n+2)$. Therefore, $|\psi(i) - \psi(j)| \leq 1$ for $0 \leq i < j \leq 3$. Hence ψ is 4-TEPC labeling.

Case 3.3: $n \equiv 2 \pmod{4}$.

Define ψ be an edge labeling function from $E(G)$ to $\{0, 1, 2, 3\}$:

$$\psi(u^{(1)}v_1^{(1)}) = 2$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\psi(u^{(1)}v_i^{(1)}) &= 1, 2 \leq i \leq \frac{n}{2} \\
\psi(u^{(1)}v_i^{(1)}) &= 3, \frac{n+2}{2} \leq i \leq n \\
\psi(u^{(2)}v_1^{(2)}) &= 1 \\
\psi(u^{(2)}v_2^{(2)}) &= 3 \\
\psi(u^{(2)}v_i^{(2)}) &= 0, 3 \leq i \leq \frac{n+2}{2} \\
\psi(u^{(2)}v_i^{(2)}) &= 2, \frac{n+4}{2} \leq i \leq n \\
\psi(u^{(j)}v_i^{(j)}) &= 0, 3 \leq j \leq k, 1 \leq i \leq \frac{n-2}{4} \\
\psi(u^{(j)}v_i^{(j)}) &= 1, 3 \leq j \leq k, \frac{n+2}{4} \leq i \leq \frac{n-2}{2} \\
\psi(u^{(2j+1)}v_i^{(2j+1)}) &= 2, 1 \leq j \leq \frac{k-2}{2}, \frac{n}{2} \leq i \leq \frac{3n-2}{4} \\
\psi(u^{(2j+1)}v_i^{(2j+1)}) &= 3, 1 \leq j \leq \frac{k-2}{2}, \frac{3n+2}{4} \leq i \leq n \\
\psi(u^{(2j+2)}v_i^{(2j+2)}) &= 3, 1 \leq j \leq \frac{k-2}{2}, \frac{n}{2} \leq i \leq \frac{3n-2}{4} \\
\psi(u^{(2j+2)}v_i^{(2j+2)}) &= 2, 1 \leq j \leq \frac{k-2}{2}, \frac{3n+2}{4} \leq i \leq n \\
\psi(u^{(j)}x_j) &= 1, 1 \leq j \leq k-1 \\
\psi(u^{(2j)}x_{2j-1}) &= 0, 1 \leq j \leq \frac{k}{2} \\
\psi(u^{(2j+1)}x_{2j}) &= 1, 1 \leq j \leq \frac{k-2}{2}.
\end{aligned}$$

We now have $\psi(0) = \psi(1) = \psi(2) = \frac{k}{2}(n+2) - 1$, $\psi(3) = \frac{k}{2}(n+2)$. Therefore, $|\psi(i) - \psi(j)| \leq 1$ for $0 \leq i < j \leq 3$. Hence ψ is 4-TEPC labeling.

Case 3.4: $n \equiv 3 \pmod{4}$.

Define ψ be an edge labeling function from $E(G)$ to $\{0, 1, 2, 3\}$:

$$\begin{aligned}
\psi(u^{(j)}v_i^{(j)}) &= 0, 1 \leq j \leq k, 1 \leq i \leq \frac{n-3}{4} \\
\psi(u^{(j)}v_i^{(j)}) &= 1, 1 \leq j \leq k, \frac{n+1}{4} \leq i \leq \frac{n-1}{2} \\
\psi(u^{(j)}v_i^{(j)}) &= 2, 1 \leq j \leq k, \frac{n+1}{2} \leq i \leq \frac{3n-1}{4} \\
\psi(u^{(j)}v_i^{(j)}) &= 3, 1 \leq j \leq k, \frac{3n+3}{4} \leq i \leq n \\
\psi(u^{(2j-1)}x_{2j-1}) &= 0, 1 \leq j \leq \frac{k}{2} \\
\psi(u^{(2j)}x_{2j-1}) &= 0, 1 \leq j \leq \frac{k}{2} \\
\psi(u^{(4j-2)}x_{4j-2}) &= 2, 1 \leq j \leq \frac{k-2}{4} \\
\psi(u^{(4j)}x_{4j}) &= 3, 1 \leq j \leq \frac{k-2}{4} \\
\psi(u^{(2j+1)}x_{2j}) &= 1, 1 \leq j \leq \frac{k-2}{2}.
\end{aligned}$$

We now have $\psi(0) = \frac{k}{2}(n+2)$, $\psi(1) = \psi(2) = \psi(3) = \frac{k}{2}(n+2) - 1$. Therefore, $|\psi(i) - \psi(j)| \leq 1$ for $0 \leq i < j \leq 3$. Hence ψ is 4-TEPC labeling.

Case 4: $k \equiv 3 \pmod{4}$.

Case 4.1: $n \equiv 0 \pmod{4}$.

Define ψ be an edge labeling function from $E(G)$ to $\{0, 1, 2, 3\}$:

$$\begin{aligned}\psi(u^{(j)}v_i^{(j)}) &= 0, 1 \leq j \leq k, 1 \leq i \leq \frac{n}{4} \\ \psi(u^{(j)}v_i^{(j)}) &= 1, 1 \leq j \leq k, \frac{n+4}{4} \leq i \leq \frac{n}{2} \\ \psi(u^{(j)}v_i^{(j)}) &= 2, 1 \leq j \leq k, \frac{n+2}{2} \leq i \leq \frac{3n}{4} \\ \psi(u^{(j)}v_i^{(j)}) &= 3, 1 \leq j \leq k, \frac{3n+4}{4} \leq i \leq n \\ \psi(u^{(2j-1)}x_{2j-1}) &= 2, 1 \leq j \leq \frac{k-1}{2} \\ \psi(u^{(2j)}x_{2j}) &= 3, 1 \leq j \leq \frac{k-1}{2} \\ \psi(u^{(j+1)}x_j) &= 1, 1 \leq j \leq k-1.\end{aligned}$$

We now have $\psi(0) = \frac{k}{2}(n+2)$, $\psi(1) = \psi(2) = \psi(3) = \frac{k}{2}(n+2) - 1$. Therefore, $|\psi(i) - \psi(j)| \leq 1$ for $0 \leq i < j \leq 3$. Hence ψ is 4-TEPC labeling.

Case 4.2: $n \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$.

Define ψ be an edge labeling function from $E(G)$ to $\{0, 1, 2, 3\}$:

$$\begin{aligned}\psi(u^{(j)}v_i^{(j)}) &= 0, 1 \leq j \leq k, 1 \leq i \leq \frac{n-1}{4} \\ \psi(u^{(j)}v_i^{(j)}) &= 1, 1 \leq j \leq k, \frac{n+3}{4} \leq i \leq \frac{n-1}{2} \\ \psi(u^{(2j-1)}v_i^{(2j-1)}) &= 2, 1 \leq j \leq \frac{k+1}{2}, \frac{n+1}{2} \leq i \leq \frac{3n+1}{4} \\ \psi(u^{(2j-1)}v_i^{(2j-1)}) &= 3, 1 \leq j \leq \frac{k+1}{2}, \frac{3n+5}{4} \leq i \leq n \\ \psi(u^{(2j)}v_i^{(2j)}) &= 3, 1 \leq j \leq \frac{k-1}{2}, \frac{n+1}{2} \leq i \leq \frac{3n+1}{4} \\ \psi(u^{(2j)}v_i^{(2j)}) &= 2, 1 \leq j \leq \frac{k-1}{2}, \frac{3n+5}{4} \leq i \leq n \\ \psi(u^{(j)}x_j) &= 1, 1 \leq j \leq k-1 \\ \psi(u^{(4j-2)}x_{4j-3}) &= 1, 1 \leq j \leq \frac{k+1}{4} \\ \psi(u^{(4j-1)}x_{4j-2}) &= 3, 1 \leq j \leq \frac{k+1}{4} \\ \psi(u^{(4j)}x_{4j-1}) &= 0, 1 \leq j \leq \frac{k-3}{4} \\ \psi(u^{(4j+1)}x_{4j}) &= 2, 1 \leq j \leq \frac{k-3}{4}.\end{aligned}$$

We now have $\psi(0) = \frac{k(n+2)-3}{2}$, $\psi(1) = \psi(2) = \psi(3) = \frac{k(n+2)-1}{2}$. Therefore, $|\psi(i) - \psi(j)| \leq 1$ for $0 \leq i < j \leq 3$. Hence ψ is 4-TEPC labeling.

Case 4.3: $n \equiv 2 \pmod{4}$.

Define ψ be an edge labeling function from $E(G)$ to $\{0, 1, 2, 3\}$:

$$\begin{aligned}
\psi(u^{(j)}v_i^{(j)}) &= 0, 1 \leq j \leq k, 1 \leq i \leq \frac{n-2}{4} \\
\psi(u^{(j)}v_i^{(j)}) &= 1, 1 \leq j \leq k, \frac{n+2}{4} \leq i \leq \frac{n-2}{2} \\
\psi(u^{(1)}v_{\frac{n}{2}}^{(1)}) &= 1 \\
\psi(u^{(1)}v_i^{(1)}) &= 2, \frac{n+2}{2} \leq i \leq \frac{3n-2}{4} \\
\psi(u^{(j)}v_i^{(j)}) &= 2, 2 \leq j \leq k, \frac{n}{2} \leq i \leq \frac{3n-2}{4} \\
\psi(u^{(j)}v_i^{(j)}) &= 3, 1 \leq j \leq k, \frac{3n+2}{4} \leq i \leq n \\
\psi(u^{(2j-1)}x_{2j-1}) &= 0, 1 \leq j \leq \frac{k-1}{2} \\
\psi(u^{(2j)}x_{2j}) &= 1, 1 \leq j \leq \frac{k-1}{2} \\
\psi(u^{(2)}x_1) &= 2 \\
\psi(u^{(j)}x_{j-1}) &= 1, 3 \leq j \leq k.
\end{aligned}$$

We now have $\psi(0) = \psi(1) = \psi(2) = \frac{k}{2}(n+2) - 1$, $\psi(3) = \frac{k}{2}(n+2)$. Therefore, $|\psi(i) - \psi(j)| \leq 1$ for $0 \leq i < j \leq 3$. Hence ψ is 4-TEPC labeling.

Case 4.4: $n \equiv 3 \pmod{4}$.

Define ψ be an edge labeling function from $E(G)$ to $\{0, 1, 2, 3\}$:

$$\begin{aligned}
\psi(u^{(j)}v_i^{(j)}) &= 0, 1 \leq j \leq k, 1 \leq i \leq \frac{n-3}{4} \\
\psi(u^{(j)}v_i^{(j)}) &= 1, 1 \leq j \leq k, \frac{n+1}{4} \leq i \leq \frac{n-1}{2} \\
\psi(u^{(j)}v_i^{(j)}) &= 2, 1 \leq j \leq k, \frac{n+1}{2} \leq i \leq \frac{3n-1}{4} \\
\psi(u^{(j)}v_i^{(j)}) &= 3, 1 \leq j \leq k, \frac{3n+3}{4} \leq i \leq n \\
\psi(u^{(4j-3)}x_{4j-3}) &= 0, 1 \leq j \leq \frac{k+1}{4} \\
\psi(u^{(2j)}x_{2j}) &= 0, 1 \leq j \leq \frac{k-1}{2} \\
\psi(u^{(4j-1)}x_{4j-1}) &= 3, 1 \leq j \leq \frac{k-3}{4} \\
\psi(u^{(2j)}x_{2j-1}) &= 1, 1 \leq j \leq \frac{k-1}{2} \\
\psi(u^{(2j+1)}x_{2j}) &= 2, 1 \leq j \leq \frac{k-1}{2}.
\end{aligned}$$

We now have $\psi(0) = \psi(1) = \psi(2) = \frac{k(n+2)-1}{2}$, $\psi(3) = \frac{k(n+2)-3}{2}$. Therefore, $|\psi(i) - \psi(j)| \leq 1$ for $0 \leq i < j \leq 3$. Hence ψ is 4-TEPC labeling. This completes the proof:

Graphs in Figures 1 to 4 show examples for case 1, case 2, case 3, and case 4 respectively.

Theorem 2 The graph $K_{1,n}$ is not 4-TEPC for $n \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$ or $n \equiv 2 \pmod{4}$.

Proof. Let $V(K_{1,n}) = \{u, v_i, 1 \leq i \leq n\}$ and $E(K_{1,n}) = \{uv_i, 1 \leq i \leq n\}$. Assume $n \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$, $n = 4t + 1$. If $K_{1,4t+1}$ is 4-TEPC, then we must have $\psi(i) = 2t + 1$ for three numbers from $\{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ and fourth one $\psi(i) = 2t$. But this is impossible since each possible 4-TEPC labeling, $\psi(uv_i) = \psi(v_i)$ and $\psi(u) = 0$. Therefore just $\psi(0)$ has odd number and $\psi(1), \psi(2)$ and $\psi(3)$ must be even number, this is a contradiction. The proof for $n \equiv 2 \pmod{4}$ is similar as above. Hence, this completes the proof.

Figure 1. The graph $\langle K_{1,4}^{(1)}, K_{1,4}^{(2)}, K_{1,4}^{(3)}, K_{1,4}^{(4)} \rangle$ and its 4-TEPC labeling

Figure 2. The graph $\langle K_{1,4}^{(1)}, K_{1,4}^{(2)}, K_{1,4}^{(3)}, K_{1,4}^{(4)}, K_{1,4}^{(5)} \rangle$ and its 4-TEPC labeling

Figure 3. The graph $\langle K_{1,5}^{(1)}, K_{1,5}^{(2)} \rangle$ and its 4-TEPC labeling

Figure 4. The graph $\langle K_{1,6}^{(1)}, K_{1,6}^{(2)}, K_{1,6}^{(3)} \rangle$ and its 4-TEPC labeling

3. CONCLUSION

We completely determined the 4-total edge product cordial labeling for some star related graphs. The labeling pattern is elucidated using illustrations. Investigate 4-total edge product cordial labeling graph of other standard graphs such complete graph, wheel related graphs (friendship, helm, closed helm, fan, double fan, web, flower, and others), and study the 5-, 6- and in general, k-total edge product cordial labeling of some star related graphs are an open area of research.

REFERENCES

- [1] R. A. Brualdi, *Combinatorial matrix classes*. Cambridge University Press, 2006, doi: 10.1017/CBO9780511721182.
- [2] G. Chartrand, C. Egan, and P. Zhang, *How to label a graph*. Springer International Publishing, 2019.
- [3] M. S. Rahman, *Basic graph theory*. Springer International Publishing, 2017.
- [4] D. B. West, *Introduction to graph theory*, 2nd ed. Prentice-Hall, New Jersey, USA, 2003.
- [5] G. S. Bloom and S. W. Golomb, "Applications of numbered undirected graphs," in *Proceedings of the IEEE*, vol. 65, no. 4, pp. 562-570, Apr. 1977, doi: 10.1109/PROC.1977.10517.
- [6] A. Kumar and A. K. Fats, "Application of graph labeling in crystallography," in *Materials Today: Proceedings 2020*, doi: 10.1016/j.matpr.2020.09.371.
- [7] P. Lalitha, M. Gayathri, L. Tamilselvi, and A. V. Arun, "Application of graceful labeling in dental arch," *Drug Invention Today*, vol. 11, no. 3, pp. 637-638, 2019.
- [8] E. Levinkov *et al.*, "Joint graph decomposition node labeling: problem, algorithms, applications," *2017 IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR)*, 2017, pp. 1904-1912, doi: 10.1109/CVPR.2017.206.
- [9] N. L. Prasanna, K. Sravanthi and N. Sudhakar, "Applications of graph labeling in communication networks," *Oriental Journal of Computer Science and Technology*, vol. 7, no. 1, pp. 139-145, 2014.
- [10] I. Cahit, "Cordial graphs: a weaker version of graceful and harmonious graphs," *Ars Combinatoria*, vol. 23, pp. 201-207, 1987.
- [11] D. Kuo, G. J. Chang, and Y. H. Kwong, "Cordial labeling of mK_n ," *Discrete Mathematics*, vol. 169, pp. 121-131, 1997.

- [12] P. L. R. Raj, and S. Koilraj, "Cordial labeling for the splitting graph of some standard graphs," *International Journal of Mathematics and Soft Computing*, vol. 1, no. 1, pp. 105-114, 2011, doi: 10.26708/IJMISC.2011.1.1.10.
- [13] M. Sundaram, R. Ponraj, and S. Somasundaram, "Product cordial labeling of graphs," *Bulletin of Pure and Applied Science*, vol. 23, pp. 155-163, 2004.
- [14] S. K. Vaidya and C. M. Barasara, "Product cordial labeling for some new graphs," *Journal of mathematics Research*, vol. 3, no. 2, pp. 206-211, 2011, doi: 10.5539/jmr.v3n2p206.
- [15] S. K. Vaidya and N. A. Dani, "Some new product cordial graphs," *Journal of Applied Computer Science and Mathematics*, vol. 8, no. 4, pp. 62-65, 2010.
- [16] S. K. Vaidya and N. B. Vyas, "Product cordial labeling in the context of tensor product of graphs," *Journal of Mathematics research*, vol. 3, no. 3, pp. 83-88, 2011, doi: 10.5539/jmr.v3n3p83.
- [17] S. K. Vaidya and C. M. Barasara, "Edge product cordial labeling of graphs," *Journal of Mathematical and Computational Science*, vol. 2, no. 5, pp. 1436-1450, 2012.
- [18] S. K. Vaidya and C. M. Barasara, "Total edge product cordial labeling of graphs," *Malaya Journal of Matematik*, vol. 3, no. 1, pp. 55-63, 2013.
- [19] A. Azaizeh, R. Hasni, A. Ahmad, and G. C. Lau, "3-total edge product cordial labeling of graphs," *Far East Journal Mathematical of Graphs Sciences*, vol. 96, no. 2, pp. 193-209, 2015, doi: 10.17654/FJMSJan2015_193_209.
- [20] U. Ali, Y. Ahmad, and M. S. Sardar, "On 3-total edge product cordial labeling of tadpole, book and flower graphs," *Open Journal of Mathematical Sciences*, vol. 4, no. 1, pp. 48-55, 2020., doi: 10.30538/oms2020.0093.
- [21] A. Azaizeh, R. Hasni, G. C. Lau and A. Ahmad, "3-Total edge product cordial labeling of complete, bipartite and generalized friendship graphs," *Utilitas Mathematica*, vol. 106, pp. 259-270, 2018.
- [22] R. Hasni and A. Azaizeh, "3-total edge product cordial labeling of wheel related graphs," *MATEMATIKA: Malaysian Journal of Industrial and Applied Mathematics*, vol. 32, no. 2, pp. 93-102, 2016.
- [23] A. Javed and M. K. Jamil, "3-total edge product cordial labeling of rhombic grid," *AKCE International Journal of Graphs and Combinatorics*, vol. 16, no. 2, pp. 213-221, 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.akcej.2017.12.002.
- [24] S. K. Vaidya, N. A. Dani, K. K. Kanani, and P. L. Vihol, "Cordial and 3-equitable labeling for some star related graphs," *International Mathematical Forum*, vol. 4, no. 31, pp. 1543-1553, 2009.
- [25] R. Hasni and A. Azaizeh, "3-total edge product cordial labeling of graphs," *AIP Conference Proceedings*, vol. 1682, 2015, Art. no. 40008, doi: 10.1063/1.4932481.

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